

**EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE SPECIFIC HEAT
CAPACITY OF GRANULAR SOY FROM LEGUMINOUS CROPS
(MEASURE)**

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Abstract: This article presents experimentally determined values of the specific heat capacity of grain soybeans from leguminous crops.

Purpose: In this article, the specific heat capacity of the granular "Selecta" soybean variety grown in Andijan region at constant pressure and constant volume at room temperature is determined experimentally.

Methods: Measurements were made on the experimental device "LD Phusica Leafies" brought from Germany to the Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute.

Results: In order to increase the accuracy of the specific heat capacity of the granular shade determined in the experimental device, the specific heat capacity of the shade was determined after measuring the granular lead, copper, and glass samples supplied with the experimental device and comparing the obtained results with the results given in the literature.

Conclusion: The specific heat capacity of granular soybean determined by the experimental method is equal to $S=0.385$ kJ/(k.kg), and it was found that the specific heat capacity of water is less than 4.19 kJ/(k.kg).

In order to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase soybean planting in the Republic in 2017-2021 and to organize the cultivation of soybean crops" dated March 14, 2017 PQ-2832, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Measures to further increase the volume of soybean cultivation in the Republic in

the decision on "events":

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the placement and cultivation of non-traditional agricultural crops in the Republic, and "Selekta", "Nafis", "Uzbek-6", "Baraka" varieties have been planted in Andijan region.

In this article, the results of specific heat capacity of "Selekta" soybean variety grown in Andijan region at constant pressure and constant volume at room temperature are determined by the experimental method.

Knowing the relative heat capacity of the product is of great importance in the quality drying and storage of granular agricultural products at a certain level of humidity.

It is known that the amount of heat ΔQ when a body is heated or cooled and released is directly proportional to the change in temperature Δt and the mass of the body m :

$$\Delta Q = C \cdot m \cdot \Delta t$$

The proportionality coefficient C in this formula is called the specific heat capacity of the body, and its value depends on the type of material.

In this experiment, the coefficient of specific heat capacity is determined in the form of samples of granular lead, copper, and glass materials. For each point, a pile of lead, copper, glass is weighed on the OHAUS CENT-O-GRAM MODEL 311 balance (310 g) and heated to temperature t_1 , the temperature of Nicr is measured with a temperature sensor (thermocouple), then the mass is determined by weighing it on the balance t_2 temperature water is poured into the colorimeter. After good mixing, the temperature t_m is reached in the state of equilibrium in which the substance is mixed with water due to heat exchange. In this case, the amount of heat released from the sample, substance is ΔQ_1

$$\Delta Q_1 = c_1 m_1 (t_1 - t_m) \quad [1]$$

where m_1 is the mass of the sample, s_1 is the specific heat capacity of the sample, the amount of heat absorbed by water is equal to ΔQ_2 .

$$\Delta Q_2 = c_2 m_2 (t_m - t_2) \quad [2]$$

Here m_2 is the mass of water.

In this case, the specific heat capacity coefficient s_2 is exact, and the temperature t_2 is assumed to be equal to the steam temperature $t_2=100^\circ\text{C}$.

The value of the unknown s_1 is calculated by the following formula based on the values of the measured t_m , t_1 , t_2 and m_2 :

$$C_1 = C_2 \cdot \frac{m_2(t_m - t_2)}{m_1(t_1 - t_m)} \quad [3]$$

The container of the colorimeter also absorbs some of the heat released from the sample. Then, the heat capacity of the colorimeter is equal to:

$$C_K = C_2 \cdot m_K \quad [4]$$

Thus, the water equivalent of the colorimeter vessel m_K is taken into account in the calculations. As a result, the amount of absorbed heat calculated by formula (2) is more accurate.

$\Delta Q_2 = c_2(m_2 + m_K)(t_m - t_2)$ and taking this into account formula (3) becomes:

$$C_1 = C_2 \cdot \frac{(m_2 + m_K)(t_m - t_2)}{m_1(t_1 - t_m)} \quad [5]$$

To perform the above calculations, we use the experimental device of Germany "LD Phusica Leafies" shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. An experimental device for determining the specific heat capacity of solids. "LD Phusica Leafits" (Germany).

Before determining the specific heat capacity of the shade in an experiment, we determine the specific heat capacity of lead, copper, and glass samples, and

after matching the values given in the literature, we begin to determine the specific heat capacity of the shade. (See Tables 1, 2)

Before starting the experiment, we pour $m=180\text{gr}$ of water into the colorimeter, we take the temperature of the sample equal to the temperature of the boiling water $t_2=100^\circ\text{C}$

Table 1 shows the values needed to measure the specific heat capacity of sample substances.

Figure 2

Table 1.

Substance name	m_2/kg	t_1	t_2
Lead	77	24,5°C	25,4°C
Copper	69	24,0°C	26,2°C
Glass	19	23,8°C	24,9°C

In the calculation, we take the equivalent mass of the colorimeter as $m_k=232$ and take the specific heat capacity of water as $C_2=4.19 \text{ kJ/k.kg}$.

Table 2 shows the experimentally determined specific heat capacities of the samples and the values obtained from the literature for comparison.

Table 2.

Substance	$C, \text{ kJ/k.kg}$	
	Experience	Results in the literature

Lead	0,133	0,1295
Copper	0,367	0,385
Glass	0,656	0,746
Soya	0,385	-----

Summary

It can be seen from the table that the experimental results correspond to the results in the literature, which means that the experiments were conducted correctly.

The specific heat capacities of lead, copper, glass and soy, which were determined in the experiment, were found to be much smaller than those of water.

Knowing the experimentally determined relative heat capacity of soybeans, it is possible to achieve energy savings in the drying of soybeans in natural and technical devices.

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